

IBRAT, THE FRIEND WHO SEARCHED FOR THE TRUE WORD

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Abstract: This article analyzes the journalistic legacy of Ishaqkhan Ibrat, a prominent representative of the Jadid movement, writer, translator, publicist, publisher and teacher, and historian. In particular, the content and essence of the advanced ideas and topical issues put forward in the articles and travel essays of the publicist published in the pages of the Turkistan Region Gazette and the Oyina magazine are highlighted.

Keywords: new method, essay, genre, travel, exam, reform, scholars, madrasas.

Ishokhon Tura Ibrat is a prominent representative of the Jadid movement, a writer, translator, publicist, publisher and teacher, and a historian who left behind an incomparable creative legacy. His creative activity as a publicist began with articles and travelogues published in the pages of the Turkistan Region Gazette and the Turkestan Gazette. In particular, the following articles have been published: "History of the Ancient City of Akhsa in the Fergana Region", "Letter to the Editor", "Isokhon Turadin's Article to the Newspaper", "Discovery of the Kokand-Naman Railway", "Letter from Türya-Kurgana", "My Information from a Trip to Tashkent", "A Trip to the City of Akhsa in the Fergana Province - About Its History", "Who Will Reform the Nation?", "The True Word". The article dedicated to the history of the city of Akhsikent is written in the essay genre, and is rich in language, interesting historical facts, and is one of the publicistic works written in an artistic style. "Akhsikent is a town in the interior of Fergana in the Movarounnahr, one of the towns on the north side of the Saihun River.... It is nine stone roads to the west of Andijan. Umar Sheikh Mirzo made it the capital" [1]. The author cites excerpts from Zahriddin Babur's "Boburnoma" and "Tarihi Rashidiya" about Akhsikent. The reader will gain a lot of information about the history of the city. The author describes in a unique way that Akhsikent was turned into ruins due to the flood of the Syrdarya River and an earthquake in 1233 AD, and that magnificent palaces, madrasas, baths, and underground passages still stand among these ruins. The article was published in the "Turkestan Viloyatining Gazeti" on June 23, 1913.

Ibrat was a close friend of the fourth son of the last khans, Khudoyor Khan, and Ibn Yaminbek. Ibn Yaminbek also collaborated with the "Turkestan Viloyatining Gazeti". In his article entitled "Isokkhan Turadin's article for the gazette", the author visited the cities of Kokand, Turakurgan, and Chust. He tells about his journey, newly built railways, and well-maintained streets. His poem, written at the house of the publicist Ibn Yaminbek, is published at the end of the article.

Here, do good and generosity to strangers,

There is a promise to the truthful, and it is victory in the hereafter.

God sent this world as a test,

How many days is the month of saving? [2]

Isokhon Ibrat's article entitled "Opening of the Kokand-Namangan Railway" was written on June 7, 1912, in connection with the opening of the Kokand-Namangan railway. The article contains

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elements typical of the reportage genre, and as the reader gets acquainted with the reality, it is described in detail that the opening of the railways was a great novelty for the local population, that streets and roads were well-maintained, that stations were built, and that jobs were created. "At the place where the train stopped, a very ornate gate was built on the Namangan side, decorated with carpets and flags, and the words "Welcome!" were written on it." The article was published in the "Turkestan Viloyati Gazeti" on July 15, 1912. The publicist's travelogue "My Information from My Tashkent Trip" is of particular importance. It was published in the "Turkestan Province Gazette" on March 2, 1914. In the instructive article, he described what he saw and experienced while taking the train from Turakurgan to Tashkent. It is noteworthy that the author, seeing the news that took place in Turkestan, modern libraries, streets with electric lights, and schools, dreams that Europeans are achieving these achievements through science, "If only our people could also benefit from this science." Ishaq Khan Ibrat, at the invitation of Munavvar Qori, participated in the exams in Tashkent several times. For example, in 1907, Munavvar Qori addressed Ishaq Khan Tura with a special invitation letter: "Dear Ishaq Khan Hoji! Starting from May 1907, the annual exams for students will begin at the "Khoniya" school in the Tarnovbashi mahalla in Tashkent. We respectfully request that if you, along with the principals of the Usuli Jadidiya schools that are under your tutelage, visit the exam sessions, the teachers and students would be pleased with you. Yours faithfully, Munavvar Qori. March 15, 1907"[3]. Thanks to this invitation, Ishaq Khan visited Tashkent several times and participated in the exams. And his series of articles dedicated to the "Usuli Jadid" and "Usuli Qil" schools were published in the "Turkestan Viloyatining Gazeti". For example, in the 72nd issue of the newspaper in 1907, the article "About Old Schools" was published. In it, the author analyzes the advantages of new-method schools and the fact that old schools are lagging behind modern developments based on examples: "It was even more pleasing to see that our Muslim children were able to speak Russian well and correctly in the exam, and that in the presence of the elders, two children asked and answered stories in turn, and gave good exams."[4] At the end of the article, Isokhon Ibrat expressed his hope that in a few years, modern specialists in the field who could contribute to the development of Turkestan would mature. Isokhon wanted to test his abilities not only as a publicist, but also as a publisher and editor. In 1913, he tried to publish a newspaper under the name "Al-tijar al-Namangan" at the "Matbaai Ishaqiya" he founded, and also applied to the government. The newspaper "Vakt", published in Ufa and famous throughout the Turkic world, writes with great pleasure about this: "The distinguished judge of Namangan, Ishak Qazi, has applied to publish a newspaper under the name "Al-tijar al-Namangan". This person opened a printing house in Namangan in 1908. This year, he opened a library under the name "Kutubkhano Ishakiya" and purchased literary books in Turkish, Tatar, and Uzbek languages. Now he is on the verge of publishing a newspaper. We sincerely wish you success."[5] However, Ibrat's dream did not come true, the tsarist government did not sign the petition, fearing that the newspaper would call on the local population to become politically active. After that, he organized a large and rich library in his house called "Kutubkhano Ishaqiya". The library contained many books on education and training written in Uzbek, Turkish, Tatar, Russian, Persian-Tajik languages. In particular, Ismoilbek Gasprinsky's "Khojai Sibyon", Saidrasul Saidazizov's "Ustodi Aval", Munavvar Qori's "Adibi Aval", "Adibi Soniy", Mahmudkhoj Behbudi's "Asbobi Ekmandi Savod", "Kitabatul-atfol" and more than 50 textbooks and manuals, as well as educational pamphlets were collected.

Ishaq Khan Ibrat also served as the judge of Turakurgan from 1897 to 1924. It was during these years that he became more active in the press with numerous journalistic articles exposing the vices

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existing in society and the evil deeds of local and colonial officials. As is known, Tsarist Russia used to hold elections for various positions under the guise of democratic criteria. In 1910, elections were held for the position of judge. In this regard, Ishaq Khan published a series of articles on the pages of the Turkistan Region Gazette exposing the true nature of the colonial system. He severely criticized the laws and regulations of the tsarist government, which gave wide opportunities to people involved in theft, bribery, and violence to become judges or thousand-heads. The government regrets that it has entrusted the fate of the people to the hands of evil, lawless, and traitors. "The regulations state in Chapter 223 that a person who is in good standing, has not been in prison for more than seven days, has not paid more than thirty sums of fines, and is not less than twenty-five years of age can be a judge. It does not say whether a scholar or an uneducated person, a fool or a wise person, or one who has learned the Sharia or the law. You see, into whose hands this great Sharia law is entrusted. There is no one who has thought and pondered." [6] Ibrat's "Who will reform the nation?" The article was published in the 12th issue of the magazine "Oyina" in 1914. In it, the publicist, along with analyzing the causes of the spiritual decline taking place in the country, calls on imams and scholars to give lectures to the people and give advice on Islamic morality. "...the Islamic morality of the people is being destroyed day by day. ...It is necessary to preach for the reform of the corruption and corruption that have increased today. It is necessary to teach and reprimand them about Islamic religion and morality." Isokkhan Ibrat congratulates the Samarkand imam, Domla Haji Abdulghafar, for giving lectures to the people on human morality based on Islamic science. The author concludes the article as follows. "When the scholars exert their efforts, the nation will certainly find reform" [7]. Ishaq Khan Ibrat deeply expressed the oppressive policy of the Russian Empire not only in his articles, but also in his socially conscious poems. For example, in the poem "Debt", the story of hardworking peasants working for meager wages, falling into debt, and losing everything they had is described with a bitter laugh in the poem.

We will not give up our debt for cotton,
He said: one day the scales will be weighed.
He spent and spent, but it never came out,
This year I will pay off the cotton.
Suddenly, a terrible debt fell on this people,
The entire people became a world-class debt.

The entry of the Russians into the Turkestan region brought negative consequences not only to the economic and social life of the native population, but also to their spiritual life. Hotels, pubs, and brothels were increasing day by day. The national hero "Bolubtur" wrote about these social problems in his satire.

Now there is no accountant, if he does one or two, he will be a threat,
The people are always in favor of the inside, and they are always in trouble.
Beloved naqshkhans, black-eyed young women
Walking in the streets, their expenses are a loss.
The poem is about history, the revolution of this era,
There are two hundred and ninety-two bayan.

Throughout the poem, the author openly criticizes the negative impact of the existing colonial system on the spirituality of the local population, the fraud of merchants, and the removal of justice and morality from the people:

Butchers, sheep traders, wars and fierce battles,

The poor are fed with meat (t) for their money.

There is no justice in the baker, and then the hay is gone,

Look, if you chop the flour, you will get forty-two loaves of bread.

No matter what genre Ishaqkhan Ibrat creates, he lives with the dream of easing the fate of the people and their difficulties. From this point of view, his poems such as “History of the Printing House”, “Masnavi about Culture”, “About the Newspaper”, “Address to the Turkistan Treaty”, “Congratulations to Namangondin”, “Pen”, “History of the Manzuma Wagon Ibratdin Yodgor”, “Muhammasi Ibrat” are noteworthy. “In these poems, the poet sharply exposed the fanatics and antiquarians who were dragging the country and the people into centuries-old backwardness. Ibrat tried to identify the causes of the hard life of the working people, poverty, backwardness of the country, and ignorance of the people, and to find ways to save them from it. [8] The new enlightener considers those who do not read newspapers to be equal to the dead or asleep in his poems, "Greetings to Namangondin", "Manzuma Ibratdin", and so on. At the same time, he calls the newspaper "a language" for the people of the world. Throughout his life, Ishaq Khan Ibrat treated every event from the point of view of the interests of his people and homeland, and dreamed of a free, independent, and prosperous life among developed nations for the future generation. His "Lughati sitta-alsina" ("Six-language dictionary"), "Jomi' ul-hutut" (Collection of writings), and the collection of poems "Divoni Ibrat", which is a collection of 30 years of poetic creativity, His scientific works on historiography "History of Fergana", "History of Culture" and "Mezon uz-zamon", and his journalistic articles published in the newspapers "Turkiston Viloyati Gazeti", "Sadoi Turkiston", "Sadoi Fergana" are an invaluable spiritual heritage of our people. In the last years of his life, such a unique talent was accused of "anti-Soviet propaganda" by the Bolshevik government and died in Andijan prison in April 1937 at the age of 75. Another sacrifice of the Motherland became a victim of the tyrannical regime. However, the meaningful and honorable life path and rich creative heritage of Ishaqkhan Ibrat are an exemplary school for our youth, an invaluable spiritual treasure.

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